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D-PHD16-4.6

A novel method to identify recombination in cgMLST profiles

This method was developed during the study of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and was included in the following pre-print publication: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. Melanie Hennart, Julien Guglielmini, Martin C.J. Maiden, Keith A. Jolley, Alexis Criscuolo and Sylvain Brisse. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>.

As a reminder, the *K. pneumoniae* species complex (KpSC) comprises seven phylogroups that have been given taxonomic status in the prokaryotic nomenclature: *K. pneumoniae* subsp. *pneumoniae* (Kp1), *K. quasipneumoniae* subsp. *quasipneumoniae* (Kp2), *K. variicola* subsp. *variicola* (Kp3), *K. quasipneumoniae* subsp. *similipneumoniae* (Kp4), *K. variicola* subsp. *tropica* (Kp5), *K. quasivariicola* (Kp6) and *K. africana* (Kp7) (Rodrigues et al., 2019). Horizontal gene transfer of large portions of the genome can occur among isolates belonging to distinct KpSC phylogroups (Holt et al., 2015). Additionally, MLST or cgMLST alleles may have been transferred horizontally from non-KpSC members, for example *E. coli*.

For the purpose of phylogeny-based classification, putative hybrid genomes were excluded. To define genomes that result from large inter-phylogroup recombination events, a novel gene-by-gene approach was developed and used, based on an original strategy as outlined below.

Detection of inter-phylogroup hybrids

To define hybrid genomes (*i.e.*, arising from multiple ancestral populations), the 45 reference genomes representative of the seven phylogroups Kp1-Kp7 (**Table 1**) were used as models. First, for each of the 7,388 other genome sequences, the closest reference genome was determined by estimating the average nucleotide identity (ANI) using FastANI v1.1 (Jain et al., 2018). Every genome *x* with ANI percentage > 99% against its closest reference genome *y* was then classified without ambiguity into the same phylogroup as the one of *y*. Second, for each genome classified into a phylogroup (Kp1-Kp7), all its cgMLST alleles were labelled with this phylogroup. Third, for each of the 629 scgMLSTv2 loci, every distinct allele associated to more than one phylogroup labels was unlabeled, given that such an allele cannot be considered as a reliable representative of a unique phylogroup (*e.g.*, it was too conserved, or involved in horizontal transfer between phylogroups). Fourth, for each locus, every unlabeled sequence identical to one of the remaining labelled alleles (*i.e.*, sequence belonging to a genome that was not assigned to a phylogroup during step 1) was labelled accordingly. Such a procedure enabled the characterization of a large set of alleles that are each representative of one of the seven phylogroups Kp1-Kp7.

As a result, almost all cgMLST profiles were mostly made up by alleles belonging to only one phylogroup label (see **Figure 1**). However, notable exceptions were observed, with some cgMLST profiles being composed of alleles belonging to two phylogroup labels (see *e.g.*, **Figure 1**). To define putative hybrid profiles, a phylogroup homogeneity index was determined for each profile, defined as the proportion of loci labelled with the predominant phylogroup (normalized by the number of non-missing alleles called in the profile). As expected, for each phylogroup Kp1-Kp7, most profiles are associated with high phylogroup homogeneity indices (see distributions in **Figure 2**). However, a total of 138 cgMLST profiles (1.9%; mainly within Kp1, Kp2 and Kp4) were associated with atypically smaller homogeneity indices, and mapping of allele phylogroup labels along the chromosome showed that many of these 138 cgMLST profiles appeared to result from large-scale inter-phylogroup recombination, while a few were made up by many unlabeled alleles (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. cgMLST profile painting illustrates large recombinations

The 7198 total (upper right) and 138 hybrid (bottom) cgMLST profiles are represented. Loci are represented in their order along the reference genome NTUH-K2044. Each allele is colored according to its attribution to a phylogroup (see color key; white: unattributed). Gene loci are indicated at the bottom of the figure. Blocs with distinctive colors within some profiles correspond to large recombination events.

Figure 2. The distribution of the phylogroup homogeneity

Each graph is based on the population of strains belonging to the indicated phylogroup. The Y-axis correspond to the number of strains (genomes) ; the X-axis corresponds to the percentage of alleles per cgMLST profile attributed to the corresponding phylogroup (see Methods). An additional panel provides details for phylogroup Kp1. Red vertical lines indicate the threshold used to define genomes as 'hybrids' (none were defined in phylogroups Kp5, Kp6 and Kp7).

Table 1. Reference genomes

Taxonomic Designation	Phylogroup	ID	Strain bank ID	Strain Name	ST	Accession Number	Reference
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	250	SB1067	SB4-2	17	ERS2786693	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1546	SB132	ATCC 13883T	3	GCA_000742135.1	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	25	SB107	MGH 78578	38	CP000647	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	252	SB1139	-	37	ERS2786694	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	412	SB617	5-2	55	ERS2786695	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	10	SB20	04A025	15	ERS2786696	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	408	SB612	2-3	133	ERS2786697	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1761	SB4938	Kp13	442	CP003999	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	398	SB3928	NTUH-K2044	23	AP006725	[1]
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1509	SB4496	BJ1-GA	380	ERS2786698	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	6432	SB11	01A030T	1528	GCA_000751755.1	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	3883	SB1124	-	2274	ERS2786699	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	3884	SB2110	U41	526	ERS2786700	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	1555	SB59	18A69	1118	ERS2786701	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	3882	SB98	Kleb Ali 0320584	622	ERS2786702	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	3881	SB1	01A065	2273	ERS2786703	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	3880	SB48	F2R9T	2263	ERS2786704	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	1512	SB579	Kp342	146	CP000964	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	7932	SB4767	At22	1220	CP001891	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	49	SB164	09A323	414	ERS2786705	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3885	SB203	12A476	384	ERS2786706	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	1554	SB30	07A044T	1215	GCA_000613225.1	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3886	SB4697	CIP110288T	2275	ERS2786707	[1]
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3887	SB610	1-1	2276	ERS2786708	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	1556	SB94	CDC 4241-71	1216	ERS2786710	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4433	SB5387	814	2466	ERS2787526	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4485	SB5439	885	2486	ERS2787527	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4577	SB5531	1266T	2561	ERS2787528	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4590	SB5544	1283	2605	ERS2787529	[1]
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4656	SB5610	1375	2600	ERS2787530	[1]
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	1508	SB33	08A119	1214	ERS2786709	[1]
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	1507	SB6071	10982	1155	GCA_000523395.1	[1]
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	6687	SB6096	KPN1705T	209	CP022823	[1]
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	6491	SB6094	01-467-2ECBU	2830	ERS2787531	[1]
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	6452	SB6095	01-310MBV	3303	ERS2787532	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	6353	SB5857	200023T	3291	ERS2787533	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	5704	-	38679	2831	ERS214332	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12476	FF1019	-	4939	SRS7014278	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12475	FF1017	-	4938	SRS7014273	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12474	FF1014	-	4938	SRS7014272	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12473	FF1011	-	4938	SRS7014271	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12472	FF1008	-	4938	SRS7014261	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12471	FF1006	-	4938	SRS7014250	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12470	FF1003	-	4938	SRS7014275	[1]
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12469	FF930	-	4938	SRS7014274	[1]

[1] Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Diallo TA, Criscuolo A, Brisse S. Description of *Klebsiella africanensis* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropicalensis* subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* subsp. nov. [published correction appears in Res Microbiol. 2019 Sep - Oct;170(6-7):300]. Res Microbiol. 2019;170(3):165-170. doi:10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003

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